

DIALECT PREFERENCES AND LANGUAGE ATTITUDES IN SAUDI MARRIAGE DECISIONS: A SOCIOLINGUISTIC PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

With an emphasis on how linguistic attitudes influence social decisions and mirror larger societal structures, this study explores dialect preferences in the context of marriage proposals in Saudi Arabia. A total of 246 parents (47 males and 199 females) and 122 daughters constituted the 368 individuals who completed two distinct surveys. Crosstabulation, chi-square tests, and descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the data. The findings indicate that the majority of parents (60.2%) preferred suitors who communicated in their dialect, with a markedly greater in-group preference observed among Najdi speakers. Speakers of the white dialect were more inclined to exhibit indifference or preference for the white dialect. Daughters had more varied responses: 25.4% selected the white dialect, 31.5% expressed no preference, and 40.8% favored the same dialect. The demographics of the daughters and their preferences shown no significant correlation. These results indicate how beliefs about language, especially dialects, influence marriage choices, identity boundaries, and societal standards. The results suggest that younger generations exhibit greater language adaptability, whereas older generations maintain stricter linguistic boundaries linked to social and geographical identity. This indicates a greater trend in the ways that language attitudes in modern Saudi society may both support and challenge social institutions.

Keywords: Language attitudes, Dialects, Marriage, Saudi Arabia.

1. INTRODUCTION

Marriage is a ubiquitous practice observed in all cultures worldwide. Its forms and ceremonies might vary significantly across different cultures. Prior study has demonstrated that nearly universal factors influence the acceptance of marriage proposals, exhibiting similarities across cultures. For example past research has revealed that girls would choose financial stability and prospective earnings in their future spouses (Amador et al., 2005). Religious similarity is yet another element that can potentially affect the acceptance of marriage by the girls (See Amador et al., 2005). Furthermore, socioeconomic standing of the mate, love and maturity were shown in various scenarios and studies (Hatfield & Sprecher, 1995). The social, cultural, financial and religious factors have gotten considerable attention from scientific studies about marriage phenomena. The inquiry now pertains to the language attitudes and their probable significance in influencing women's approval of marriage. To be more explicit, may the language attitudes towards a specific social group negatively or positively effect the acceptance or rejection of the mate?

Language attitudes have a longstanding history of exposing the adverse effects that might arise in legal circumstances, resulting in linguistic discrimination (Dixon et al., 2002). Discrimination in housing markets (Massey & Lundy, 2001; Purnell et al., 1999; Wright, 2023). Furthermore, discrimination in the assessment of job applicants (ATKINS, 1993; Deprez-Sims & Morris, 2010). Collectively, past study demonstrated that less

standard and prestigious language variety speakers endure social inequity. Knowledge about the influence of linguistic attitudes in marital contexts remains limited.

A deeper comprehension of girls and their families' perceptions of suitors' spoken accents and dialects is crucial for the progression of language attitude theory, particularly concerning the phenomena of intermarriage and language attitudes in a broader context. From a sociolinguistics standpoint, a comprehensive understanding of attitudes towards the suitor's accent or dialect is essential for formulating effective ways to assist suitors in obtaining their social rights to marry their desired partners. Such measures and support are necessary for the suitors' well-being and social equality.

The present study seeks to contribute to the advancement of language attitudes theory in one hand and to offer strategies to enhance social equality. The study is preliminary and gathered data from five regions in Saudi Arabia regarding their language attitudes towards the dialect of suitors. The objective of the study is to ascertain the existence of a problem and to determine whether the suitor's dialect may serve as a potential indicator of language attitudes in marital circumstances. The finding of the survey revealed that only Najdi participants have shown preference to the suitors to speak their own dialect. Consequently, additional research is required to explore underlying attitudes. Najd is the central region of Saudi Arabia, and its speakers are regarded as the most prestigious due to several historical and political factors that confer prominence onto the dialect. Data were gathered through an online questionnaire featuring direct inquiries.

Research Questions

- Is the suitor's dialect a determining factor in the acceptance or rejection of marriage proposals by girls and their parents with daughters of marriageable age?
- If so, then what are the social groupings in Saudi Arabia that would see the dialect as a deciding factor?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Language Attitudes Construct

The tripartite model posits that language attitudes comprise three components: affect (the emotions individuals possess toward an attitude object), cognition (the beliefs individuals maintain about an attitude object), and behavior (the behaviors directed toward an attitude object). In social psychology, these three components collectively constitute an evaluative response to an item. Therefore, as the focus of this paper is language, I refer to the definition proposed by Dragojevic et al., (2021, p. 2), which characterizes attitudes as "evaluative reactions to a language." Dragojevic et al. categorizes evaluative reactions to a language into two components: reactions to the language variety itself and reactions to the speaker of that language variation. The two evaluative responses are closely interconnected. This study will examine the evaluative responses to the speaker of the linguistic variety. Prior research indicates that evaluative reactions (attitudes) towards speakers of various language varieties yield significant outcomes, as less standard and less prestigious language forms face undermined opportunities, particularly in employment and housing markets. In the following section, I will discuss the prior study that focused on implications of language attitudes.

2.2. Previous Studies on the Social and Behavioral Repercussions of Language Attitudes

Past research on the implications of language attitudes sees attitudes as input that influences the output in various ways. In other words, this line of research does not only focus on attitudes itself with its construct and how it is constructed but rather it focuses on how attitudes impact people decisions. Investigating language attitudes is crucial for assessing the impact of reactions to these attitudes and then proposing solutions to the research problem (Garrett, 2010; Garrett et al., 2003).

Previous study has demonstrated outcomes in numerous scenarios. In housing rental scenarios, Massey and Lundy (2001) did a study on Philadelphia metropolitan region to reveal whether race, gender and class would effect the landlords decisions to rent their dwellings. It was shown that lower-class Black females had the least opportunities to rent housing compared to middle-class white guys. In a similar vein, Purnell et al., (1999) conducted an experiment involving telephone interviews with landlords, during which three dialects were selected and modified in each call. The three dialects were African American English Vernacular (AAEV), Chicago English (ChE), and Standard American English (SAE). They discovered that the landlord exhibited discrimination against the non-standard dialects, specifically AAVE and ChE.

Rakić et al., (2011) discovered that job candidates with regional German accents experienced prejudice and

diminished employment opportunities compared to those with standard German accents. Surprisingly, Roessel et al., (2019) revealed that even nonnative accented listeners decreased the work appropriateness for non-native accented speakers.

Collectively, earlier research suggested a language attitude pattern where the judgment based on linguistic signals were obvious in numerous scenarios where nonstandard and nonnative accents did not receive equal chances to natives and standard accents. Although earlier studies have covered numerous contexts but still to my knowledge no study have tapped into the effects of language attitudes on the acceptance or refuse of marriage proposal. Marriage appears to be influenced by overt variables, including social, cultural, financial, and religious elements; nevertheless, the pertinent question arises as to whether it is also impacted by hidden factors, such as attitudes towards the suitor's dialect. Therefore, the present study chose Saudi Arabia as the context of the study and Saudi families as the population of the study. In the subsequent section, I will briefly review previous language attitudes research in Saudi Arabia.

2.3. Language Attitudes Research in Saudi Arabia

Research on language attitudes is an expanding field in Saudi Arabia and has received minimal attention in recent years. The recent research mostly concentrated on Saudi dialects and sub-dialects to explore the stereotypical perceptions of Saudis regarding their dialects. Part of the earlier studies were meant to extract qualitative data, for example, Al-Rojaie, (2021) conducted a perceptual study in SA where 649 Saudi individuals were recruited for the study. The study incorporated a labeling task in which participants assigned attitudinal labels to each dialect in Saudi Arabia. His findings indicated various evaluation profiles. Similarly, Alhazmi & Alfalig, (2022) employed keyword technique where they requested Saudi participants to jot down their attitudes regarding Saudi dialects which were provided to them theoretically. Both prior research demonstrated various evaluative profiles towards Saudi dialect where Najdi and Hijazi dialect was seen as the most positive with descriptors such as 'clear', 'dominant' 'prestigious' for the Najdi dialect and 'urban' friendly' 'easy to understand' for the Hijazi dialect. The southern dialect is associated with negative connotations such as "uncultured". The eastern dialect was classified in terms of its phonetic traits 'vowel lengthening' and 'heavy accented'. The northern dialect was linked to traditional and moralistic values, like 'Bedouin' and 'generous.'

Another line of research in language attitudes has focused on quantitative methodologies to elucidate the attitudinal dimensions in Saudi society. (Alhazmi, 2023) researched LAs towards Saudi dialects where 568 Saudi engaged in an online questionnaire that employed verbal guise technique. Factor analysis revealed three dimensions: Dynamism-status, Dynamism-language, and solidarity. The Najdi dialect exhibited "the fullest evaluative profile in the two-type dynamism factor" (Alhazmi 2023:8), while the southern dialect was the least related with Dynamism dimensions. The northern dialect is most closely related with the dimension of solidarity, while the eastern dialect appears to exhibit the least solidarity. In a comparable perspective, Alhazmi, (2024) researched LAs towards an endangered language variety in SA (named Faifi variety). The study employed conceptual method and collected data from 258 the indigenous people of Faifa. The analysis unveiled two dimensions: status and dynamism. Notably the characteristic 'educated' developed within the dynamism dimension rather than its default place within the status dimension. Alhazmi ascribed this surprising result to the lack of the language variety being taught in schools. Furthermore, Alhazmi observed that age factor was a relevant one with older generation had more positive attitudes towards the linguistic variety than the younger generation.

2.4 Factors that Affect Marriage Decision in Saudi Arabia

Marriage proposals in Saudi Arabia are arranged by families. That is the family of the suitor generally approach the family of the girl at marriageable age. The two families become acquainted, and most significantly, the suitor and the groom meet at Alshofa Alshariya¹ to familiarize themselves with one another. Consequently, the choice to accept the marriage proposal is a collaborative one, made by both sets of parents, the suitor, and the young woman. Research in SA has shown that religious commitment, lineage and genealogy, social status, educational level, cultural background, emotions/love and behavioural commitment in family life were the most revealed criteria used by parents and their daughters to help them accept or refuse a marriage proposal (Alqahtany & Althiabi, 2024).

¹ "Al-Shoufa Al-Shar'iyya" is the Islamic practice where a man, with family approval, is allowed to see the woman he intends to propose to.

2.5. Main dialects in Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia is a big country with rich culture and various accents. The dialects utilized in Saudi Arabia are spatially constrained (Ingham, 1994; Prochazka, 1988). They are categorized into five primary dialects in Saudi Arabia: the central dialect (also known as the Najdi dialect), the northern dialect, the eastern dialect, the southwestern dialect, and the western dialect (sometimes referred to as the Hijazi dialect) ((Aldarsoni, 2011; Al-Rojaie, 2021).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Methods

The primary method of the study is an online survey. Online questionnaires are commonly employed in language attitudes research and it proven its success (Garrett, 2010; Kircher & Zipp, 2022). The questionnaire of the study contains information sheet and consent form. It furthermore, includes filtering questions that ask participant to self-identify themselves, if they are:

- A girl of marriageable age
- Parents of daughters of marriageable age
- None of them

I have developed a chain survey for each choice mentioned above, guiding participants through their adaptive questionnaires. The questionnaire design for the girls and the parents is generally the same the only difference between them is the manner of addressing the questions for example when I am asking the parents, I ask them about their preferred dialect that they wish the suitor of their daughter speak it. When the inquiry is posed to the females, it will inquire about their favorite dialects for potential suitors, among other topics. Regarding the final selection (none of them), I devised a chain survey that includes a thank you note for the participants, informing them that they are not included in the study..

Most crucially, the initial section of the questionnaire was including general questions like the preferred age of the suitors, the chosen employment sector of the suitor, the preferred wage of the suitor and so on. Although these questions are not related to the purpose of the study but the justification for introducing them before questioning the participants about the preferred dialect of the suitor is that I don't want the participants to feel that the whole study is merely focusing on dialect preference of the suitor to avoid social desirability bias (Garret 2010). Consequently, I have presented them with several broad inquiries to convey that the study encompasses multiple aspects beyond merely the dialect factor. I will refrain from analyzing the introductory questions and will focus solely on the findings related to the research topic concerning the preferred dialect of the suitor, as expressed by the parents and the girls.

The final section of the questionnaire gathers information regarding participants' social background, including age, spoken dialect, region of residence in Saudi Arabia, and gender (applicable only in the parents' questionnaire).

3.2 Procedures

The questionnaire was distributed online using social media platform such as WhatsApp and Twitter and it took place in September 2024. The study's target group was all Saudi girls of marriageable age and their parents. The sampling technique employed is convenience sampling, wherein the questionnaire is disseminated to a readily accessible sample. Although results from convenience sampling cannot be generalized as the sample might not represent the whole population but convenience sampling is useful in exploratory research, where the aim in the current study to gather initial insights about attitudes towards the dialect of the suitor in SA rather than to generalize findings to the entire population.

3.3. Participants

The study participants were 368. The parent questionnaire included 246 participants: 47 males and 199 females. The questionnaire for girls had 122 participants

3.4. Statistical Analysis

Data were examined employing descriptive statistics, Chi-square testing, and cross-tabulation.

4. FINDINGS

In this section, I will present the analysis of first parents' questionnaire and then the second section about daughters' questionnaire. Each section will include two parts of analysis: findings regarding the preferred dialect of the suitor and also analyzing if there is any social background effects that significantly affected the findings. Second, analyzing the reasons behind their choice to a specific dialect and revealing the most common ones

4.1. Parents' questionnaire findings

Findings reveal that the majority of parents have preferred that the suitor of their daughter to speak the same dialect as their own. See Table 1.

Table 1 – Parents' Preferred Dialect of Suitor

Dialect preference	Frequency	Percent
Same as mine	153	60.2
White dialect ²	48	18.9
Doesn't matter	53	20.9
Total	254	100.0

The data indicates that 60.2% of parents share a preference similar to mine about their daughter's suitor's marriage proposal. The subsequent inquiry is whether any demographics have influenced the parents' choices.

4.1.1. Effects of Demographics

Chi-Square test was used to reveal if there is any significant results that have been affected by demographics, see table 2 below.

Table 2 – Chi-Square Test Results for Parents' Dialect Preference by Demographics

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	94.516a	14	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	103.604	14	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.829	1	.093
N of Valid Cases	246		

Findings indicate that there are discernible variations among the factors. That is the p value shows that there is significance among variables (i.e. demographics) and the choice of the preferred dialect. Upon further examination of the results, I conducted a crosstabulation to identify the specific demographic groupings influencing the outcomes. Refer to Table 3 below.

² In the Saudi Arabian context, the white dialect refers to a neutral, widely intelligible variety of Arabic that lacks strong regional markers. It is often spoken in urban centers and serves as a linguistic bridge among speakers of different regional dialects.

Table 3 – Crosstabulation of Parents' Preferred Dialect by Their Spoken Dialect

		What is your spoken dialect?							
		Southern dialect	Northern dialect	Eastern dialect	Urban Bedouin Hijazi dialect	Hadari Hijazi dialect	Najdi dialect	White dialect	Other
Same as mine	Count	20	12	0	24	19	70	4	1
	Expected Count	15.2	12.8	1.8	21.3	20.1	50.6	26.2	1.8
	% within Q5 - What dialect would you prefer the man who proposes to your daughter to speak?	13.3%	8.0%	0.0%	16.0%	12.7%	46.7%	2.7%	0.7%
	% within Q8 – what is your spoken dialect	80.0%	57.1%	0.0%	68.6%	57.6%	84.3%	9.3%	33.3%
	% of Total	8.1%	4.9%	0.0%	9.8%	7.7%	28.5%	1.6%	0.4%
	Standardized Residual	1.2	-.2	-1.4	.6	-.3	2.7	-4.3	-.6
The white dialect	Count	0	6	2	3	4	9	23	0
	Expected Count	4.8	4.0	.6	6.7	6.3	15.9	8.2	.6
	% within Q5 - What dialect would you prefer the man who proposes to your daughter to speak?	0.0%	12.8%	4.3%	6.4%	8.5%	19.1%	48.9%	0.0%
	% within Q8 - What is your spoken dialect?	0.0%	28.6%	66.7%	8.6%	12.1%	10.8%	53.5%	0.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	2.4%	0.8%	1.2%	1.6%	3.7%	9.3%	0.0%
	Standardized Residual	-2.2	1.0	1.9	-1.4	-.9	-1.7	5.2	-.8
Doesn't matter	Count	5	3	1	8	10	4	16	2
	Expected Count	5.0	4.2	.6	7.0	6.6	16.5	8.6	.6

The table above demonstrates that of the four demographics that have been investigated (age, gender, spoken dialect, degree of education) the spoken dialect of the parents is the only variable that have affected the statistics. The findings indicate that the Standardized Residual for the Najdi dialect is +2.7, suggesting that a greater number of Saudis who speak the Najdi dialect prefer suitors for their daughters to also speak the same dialect than anticipated. Thus the Najdi spoken dialect here is a key factor to the outcomes.

Secondly, the Standardized Residual for the white dialect-same dialect is -4.3, indicating that a significantly lower number of those who speak the white dialect want suitors for their daughters to speak the same dialect (white or any dialect) than anticipated. Unfortunately, the quiz here didn't ask this specific group whether the same dialect here would represent their white dialect or their original dialect. It is because that the white dialect in Saudi Arabia is not tied to one group or one region, it is many times utilized by people from different areas in the country for mutual intelligibility. Thus, there is no clear-cut analysis for this particular answer. I am uncertain whether participants who speak the white dialect and then select the same dialect are referencing their white dialect or another dialect they also speak alongside it.

Third, the Standardized Residual for the southern dialect compared to the white dialect is -2.2, indicating that a significantly lower number of Saudi parents of southern dialect speakers desire their daughter's suitors to speak the white dialect than expected.

Fourth, The Standardized Residual for the white dialect is +5.2, indicating that a greater number of Saudi parents who speak the white dialect prefer suitors for their daughters to also speak the white dialect than anticipated. Thus, the white spoken dialect here is a key factor to the outcomes.

Fifth, the Standardized Residual for the choice 'doesn't matter' -white dialect is +2.5, this shows that more

Saudi parents with the white spoken dialect are not interested with the dialect of the suitor than expected.

Overall, the results indicate that parents who speak the Najdi dialect prefer suitors who also speak the same dialect. Secondly, parents who communicate in the white dialect either like suitors to also speak this dialect or are indifferent to the subject.

4.2. Findings from the Daughters Questionnaire

The selection of the suitor's favorite dialect has a distinct trend compared to the parents' questionnaire. See table 4 below

Table 4 – Daughters' Preferred Dialect of Suitor

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Same as mine	53	40.8	40.8	40.8
White dialect	33	25.4	25.4	66.2
Other	3	2.3	2.3	68.5
Doesn't matter	41	31.5	31.5	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The results show that 40.8% of daughters preferred suitors who speak the same dialect as theirs, indicating a moderate inclination toward linguistic similarity. However, a significant portion (31.5%) expressed no preference, and 25.4% favored the white dialect, reflecting more flexible attitudes. Only 2.3% selected "other," suggesting minimal preference for less common dialects. Chi-square analysis revealed no statistically significant relationship between daughters' dialect preferences and their demographic variables, indicating that factors such as age or regional background did not influence their choices.

5. DISCUSSION

This study provides preliminary evidence that dialect preferences influence marriage decisions in Saudi Arabia, particularly among specific social groupings. The most obvious pattern found among Najdi-speaking parents, who exhibited a marked preference for suitors speaking the same dialect. This corroborates previous research indicating that languages linked to elevated status or reputation frequently confer social advantages (Dragojevic et al., 2021). Given the historical and political relevance of Najd in the development of the Saudi state (Ingham, 1994), it is possible that language uniformity in this region is viewed as a means of preserving lineage, identity, and perceived cultural superiority.

In contrast, speakers of the white dialect exhibited linguistic adaptability, either favoring the white dialect or demonstrating indifference. This coincides with the white dialect's sociolinguistic role as a neutral, urban variety that fosters communication across disparate groups (Alhazmi & Alfalig, 2022). The preference for the white dialect, which is not confined to a certain location and is frequently spoken in both formal and informal public conversation, may indicate a more integrative identity rather than a regional one.

A notable generational disparity was seen between parents and daughters. While the majority of parents emphasized dialectal congruence, daughters displayed a more varied distribution of choices, with a considerable portion expressing no preference at all. This may reflect a generational shift in linguistic views, echoing findings from recent studies indicating younger Saudis display more flexible or neutral appraisals of dialects (Alhazmi, 2024). This move may indicate deeper transformations within Saudi culture, where younger generations are gaining more personal freedom and mixing more across regions, instead of strictly following traditional family-based rules. Collectively, the findings demonstrate how language attitudes, while frequently covert, connect with overt social decisions like marriage.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study is limited by its use of convenience sampling, which reduces the generalizability of the findings to the broader Saudi population. Furthermore, the questionnaire design failed to specify whether respondents referring to "same dialect" were indicating white dialects or regional dialects, resulting in interpretive ambiguity. Future research should apply stratified sampling to assure regional coverage and incorporate qualitative approaches, such as interviews, to understand the motivations behind dialect preferences. Broadening the scope to encompass male viewpoints and under-researched dialect groups would yield a more thorough comprehension of linguistic attitudes in marital circumstances throughout Saudi Arabia.

7. CONCLUSION

This study examined the influence of dialect preferences on marriage decisions in Saudi Arabia, emphasizing the interplay between language attitudes, social identity, tradition, and generational shifts. The findings demonstrated a considerable preference among Najdi-speaking parents for suitors who share their dialect, suggesting the persisting effect of regional identity and perceived prestige. In contrast, white dialect speakers displayed increased linguistic flexibility, presumably reflecting a shift toward more inclusive social norms. Notably, daughters showed more diversified choices, with many expressing indifference toward dialect of the suitor suggesting a generational shift in language attitudes. These patterns underline the subtle significance of language in social decision-making and the persistence of dialect-based biases, even in intimate life choices like marriage. While the study provides significant preliminary insights, it also underscores the need for further research employing qualitative and more representative sampling approaches. Overall, the research contributes to the increasing body of sociolinguistic literature on language attitudes in the Arab world.

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